

Metal Chelates of NN-di(thiocarbamoyl) Hydrazine with Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Fe(II) and Mn(II)

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Manuscript received 21 June 1976, revised 11 July 1979, accepted 11 August 1979

Preparation of NN'-di(thiocarbamoyl) hydrazinate (DTU) metal chelates of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Fe(II) and Mn(II), is described. The metals form 1 : 1 chelates with the ligand. Infrared spectral data of the ligand and the metal chelates suggest that DTU is coordinated to metal ions as a tetra dentate ligand. The electronic spectra and magnetic properties suggest octahedral configuration for the metal chelates.

THE thiourea derivatives of hydrazine, such as, dithiocarbamido-hydrazine¹ and dialkyl dithio dicarbamido hydrazine²⁻⁵ have been used as analytical agents. Structural studies on metal complexes of these thiourea derivatives have received limited attention. Jensen and coworkers⁶ first reported the Ni(II) complex of N-thiocarbamoyl-N' (carbamoyl, thiocarbamoyl) hydrazine while Ahmed and coworkers⁷⁻⁸ later reported a few more of the metal chelates of N-thiocarbamoyl-N'-carbomoyl hydrazine derivatives. A novel method of the syntheses of dithiourea and a number of new thiourea derivatives of hydrazine has been recently reported by Nayak and coworkers⁹ from this laboratory. These compounds have been found to be powerful complexing agents and a programme of work on the preparation of their complexes and characterisation has been undertaken by us. In the present communication we report the complexes of divalent transition metals, namely Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Fe(II) and Mn(II) with the ligand NN'-di (thiocarbamoyl) hydrazine.

Experimental

The ligand (NH₂ - CS - NH)₂ (H₂DTU) was prepared following the procedure reported by Nayak and coworkers⁹ (M.P., 218°).

NN'-di(thiocarbamoyl)hydrazinal metal(II), M(DTU),
M = Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Fe(II), Mn(II) :

An alcoholic solution of the ligand or its sodium salt in water was added to an equimolar aqueous solution of the corresponding metal halide (in the case of Fe(II), ferrous ammonium sulphate was taken) and the pH of the solution was raised to 6-7 with dilute sodium hydroxide (0.1 N) (except for Cu(II) complex), when the complex precipitated. The precipitates were digested on a water bath for 30 minutes, filtered, washed with water followed by ethanol and dried in vacuum.

The metal content of each complex was determined by the standard procedures. Sulphur was estimated as barium sulphate¹⁰. The carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen in the complexes were determined by semi-micro combustion process. The analytical data are recorded in Table 1.

The complexes are found to be sparingly soluble in water. Freshly prepared samples are slightly soluble in ethanol, acetone and dioxan.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE METAL CHELATES

Formula of Chelates	Colour	Melting Point or Decomposition at Temp. °C	μ_{eff} in B.M. $22 \pm 1^\circ \text{C}$	Metal%		Sulphur%		Nitrogen%		Carbon%		Hydrogen%	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1. Cu(DTU)	Bluish-black	230 Decomposes	1.7	30.6	30.07	29.86	30.86	25.75	26.51	12.07	11.37	2.75	1.91
2. Ni(DTU)	Deep-cream	240	2.2	27.8	28.39	29.18	30.96	26.34	27.09	12.87	11.61	2.28	1.95
3. Co(DTU)	Midgreen	240	3.7	27.4	28.5	29.7	30.93	28.45	27.07	11.38	11.61	2.48	1.95
4. Fe(DTU)3H ₂ O	Chocolate	230	3.4	21.38	21.64	31.41	31.33	20.63	21.72	10.08	9.91	3.85	3.91
5. Mn(DTU)	Light-brown	240	5.4	27.70	27.54	30.04	30.9	20.27	21.93	10.92	11.83	1.70	1.99

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Physical measurements :

The conductance measurements of the complexes in non-aqueous solvents were carried out by Philip's Conductivity Bridge. Magnetic susceptibility measurements of the solid complexes at room temperatures were made by Gouy method, using mercury(II)-tetrathiocyanato cobaltate(II) as the calibrating agent. The diamagnetic corrections were made using the constants given by Lewis and Wilkins¹¹. Infrared spectra of the ligand and the complexes were recorded in KBr pellets on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer model 221. Electronic spectra of the freshly prepared complexes and the ligand were taken in dioxan medium.

Results and Discussion

The ligand may be postulated to exist in the following three different structural forms :

On the basis of our findings from acid dissociation measurements, i.r. and electronic spectra, we are led to believe that the ligand exists in equilibrium in the keto (I) and enol(II) tautomeric forms. The i.r. spectrum of the ligand shows a number of N-H stretching vibrations in the region 3200 cm⁻¹ and another band at 1620 cm⁻¹ attributed to NH₂ deformation. Since the latter band is unexpected for structure(III), we rule out the possibility* of the existence of the ligand in this form.

The electronic spectrum of the ligand shows an intense band at 253 nm and another band of weaker

intensity at 210 nm. These features in UV region are characteristics of a conjugated compound and provide evidence for structure(II).

The acid dissociation constants of the ligand have been measured by Bjerrum-Calvin method as modified by Irving and Rossotti¹² (to be published) and show that K₁ and K₂ have the values 7.0 × 10⁻¹⁰ and 6.2 × 10⁻¹³ respectively. These dissociation constant provide evidence for the existence of the enolic form and strongly imply that the anionic form of the ligand would act as a good nucleophilic agent.

Structure of the complexes :

The infrared spectra of the complexes (Table 2) in the higher frequency region (3400-3000 cm⁻¹) show the band positions unshifted in the chelates as compared to the ligand, indicating that the coordination through nitrogen of the NH₂ group has not taken place. The width of the band in the free ligand indicates that the N-H groups are involved in hydrogen bonding either inter or intramolecular. The i.r. spectra of thiourea and some of their metal complexes also show similar features in this region of the spectrum¹³⁻¹⁵.

The band at ~2400 cm⁻¹ has been attributed to ν(S-H) vibration¹⁶. This band is absent in the metal complexes. Two bands at ~1610 cm⁻¹ and 1545 cm⁻¹ are observed for the ligand. The former is unshifted in the complexes and is assigned to deformation vibration of NH₂ group while the latter is shifted to 1520-1495 cm⁻¹ and is assigned to C=N stretching vibrations indicating the coordination of azido nitrogen with the metal ions.

The band near about 1400 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to C=S stretching vibration in the ligand^{13,15}. In

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA OF NN'-DI(THIOCARBAMOYL) HYDRAZINE AND ITS METAL CHELATES IN cm⁻¹

Ligand H ₂ DTU	Cu(DTU)	Ni(DTU)	Co(DTU)	Fe(DTU), H ₂ O	Mn(DTU)
3350 s	3450 s 3300-3400 sbd	3480 s 3360 s	3420 sbd 3260 sbd	3200-3430 sbd 3140 w	3220-3440 mbd
2400 m					
1610 s	1605 s	1605 s	1605 s	1610 s	1605 s
1600 s					
1545 s	1512 s	1510 s	1515 s	1510 s	1520 m
1495 s		1495 s			
1375 m	1305 s	1310 s	1305 s	1320 m	1315 s
1300-1340 wbd					
1180 m					
1055 m	1120 m	1105 s	1100 s	1125 m 1030 m	1120 m 1025 w
840 m		995 w 950 w			
790 m	790 w	745 s	745 s	740 m	730 s
725 m	730 m 525-600 mbd	660 w	630 w	705 w 600 m	630 m 520 m
	440 m	440 m	450 w	600 m 520 w 450 w	395 m 320 m
	380 w	380 m			

the metal complexes this band is lowered to about 1300 cm^{-1} clearly manifesting the sulphur atom of the C=S group to be involved in coordination.

Besides a strong and sharp band is observed at about 790 cm^{-1} in the ligand and has been attributed to the coupled bands of $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$. This band on coordination with metal complexes shifts to a lower frequency region and appears near about 745 cm^{-1} clearly implying the coordination of sulphur and nitrogen atoms.

Electronic spectra and magnetic properties :

The magnetic moments of the metal complexes are found to be below the normal values expected for octahedral complexes. Similarly the electronic spectra can be interpreted by assuming octahedral or more reasonably the tetragonally distorted octahedral ligand field around the metal ion.

The copper complex possesses the magnetic moment 1.7 B.M. and its electronic spectrum shows a broad asymmetric band at $19,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ followed by another strong band near $26,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The former approximates to ${}^3\text{E}_g \rightarrow {}^2\text{T}_{2g}$ transition in an octahedral ligand field. The width and asymmetry of this band suggests tetragonal distortion due to coordination to hetero atoms and also Jahn-Teller effect. The latter band arises due to intra-ligand transition and charge transfer.

The nickel complex possesses magnetic moment 2.2 B.M. which is appreciably below the normal value 2.9-3.4 B.M. observed for octahedral complexes. The electronic spectrum of the complex shows a broad asymmetric band near $16,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ followed by strong intra-ligand transition near $26,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a shoulder at $22,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The ligand field bands can be assigned to ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}$ and ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ transitions respectively. These seem to approximate to the tetragonally distorted octahedral field.

The cobalt(II) complex also shows considerably low magnetic moment, the value being 3.7 B.M. Its electronic spectrum shows an intense band at $15,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a shoulder at $17,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. In an octahedral approximation these bands can be assigned to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2g}$ and ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ respectively.

The magnetic moment for the manganese(II) complex is found to be 5.4 B.M. which is also lower than the normally expected value of 5.9 B.M. for a spin free octahedral manganese(II) ion. The electronic spectra exhibit a weak shoulder at $20,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a charge transfer or intra-ligand transition near $24,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The iron(II) complex possesses a magnetic moment of 3.4 B.M. No significant transition is observed in the visible region of the spectrum.

Considering the trans structure of the ligand to be more stable than the cis form, the i.r., electronic and magnetic moment data suggest the following probable structure for the complexes (Fig. IV). The low magnetic moment can be said to arise due to spin exchanges process involving sulphur atom.

The high insolubility in water and common organic solvents of the complexes suggest their polymeric structure. The tetragonally distorted octahedral structure of the complexes may be due to intermolecular linkages.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Professor S. Pani, Head of the Chemistry Department, Sambalpur University, for providing laboratory facilities. One of the authors (T.D.M.) is indebted to Sambalpur University for the Junior Research Fellowship.

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